

SUGGESTED SOLUTIONS

FOR PROFESSORS

1. Explanation using blackboard and projector – reinforce the concept using Kahoot

It is important to make clear to the learner that this anti-pattern exists. For this, a solution suggestion would be:

1. Bring to class code snippets with antipatterns related to previously presented topics with at most one error per line
2. show them to the learners
3. ask them to point out some error
4. ask if someone in class could explain the consequences of the error for the program
5. reinforce the explanation, if possible, showing other examples of the same error
6. explain the correct way to write the command (line), without the error
7. rewrite the line on the blackboard, without the error, or make the correction visible on the projector
8. repeat steps 3 to 7 as long as there are errors in the code
Then (it is necessary for the teacher's computer and the learners' phones or computers to have Internet access):
9. show the password for the previously prepared kahoot quiz and ask learners to connect to kahoot with their phone
10. If this method has not been used before with them, explain the "game"
11. start the "game", cheer each learner's victory, and make notes on the questions they fail most often
12. In the end, present the results and go back to the exercises they had the most difficulty with.

P.S: The teacher will obtain a valuable resource, as it will become clear on which topics students need reinforcement and may address them further during class.

2. Groups working with step-by-step execution to understand errors – reinforce with exercises

It is important to make clear to the learner that this anti-pattern exists. For this, a solution suggestion would be:

1. assemble teams of 2 or 3 students;
2. give the teams codes with the error. Not necessarily the same code for all teams;
3. ask them to do a step-by-step execution of the code presented;
4. then ask for a team to show the class what they have found and explain how they got this result;
5. ask others with the same snippet if they had different results. If so, ask them to present to the class;
6. now you (instructor), using visuals, simulating computer memory space, for instance, show, correct or reinforce what was presented;
7. repeat steps 3 through 6 if you have more than one type of exercise;
8. give them exercises to solve in which they could make the mistakes mentioned above;
9. ask them to solve on the blackboard so you can correct them if the mistake still appears.

3. Programming in front of the students, making the error appear – reinforce by asking students to develop new codes

It is important to make clear to the learner that this anti-pattern exists. For this, a solution suggestion would be:

1. ask learners to solve an exercise in which the error you want to address might happen;
2. go to the blackboard and expose a superficial outline of what the code needs to do and in what sequence;
3. use the projector to start programming on the computer in front of the students;
4. make the error appear;
5. compile and ask the learners for suggestions on how the code could be fixed;
6. test each suggestion and explain if necessary, the reasons why it did not work;
7. finish with working code projected for learners to see;
8. give them one more exercise to solve;
9. ask a learner to develop their code right on the computer to project for all;
10. explain what is happening while the learner is typing;
11. repeat steps 8 through 10 as many times as you like, using intensive practice for learning.

4. Apply the bench test (table test) in code samples with and without the error, compare the results – reinforce by asking the students to solve some exercises

It is important to make clear to the learner that this anti-pattern exists. For this, a solution suggestion would be:

1. show an example of the error to the learner. Make sure the only mistake in your example is the one you want to address;
2. make it very clear, highlighting the mistake with a colored circle or arrow;
3. explain why it is wrong;
4. do a bench test (table test) showing what happens;
5. fix the code, and redo the bench test (table test);
6. compare the results;
7. make sure the learners understand by asking them to do one or two exercises like this, but with other code snippets.
8. correct during class, in the presence of the learners.

FOR STUDENTS

1. Solve exercises, add code errors, and ask classmate to find them

Learners may study this antipattern to avoid it in the future with an exercise:

Note: It is important that students work with at least one peer and that they have a computer to work on the exercise.

1. Study some of the antipatterns of a given topic
2. Choose similar exercises that depend on the topic and solve them independently
3. After the exercises are done and error-free with correct outputs, each one copies their code to paper with added errors (each one chooses how many errors to add)
4. Switch papers
5. Each one corrects their peer's exercise, pointing out the errors found
6. When done, learners check with their peer, who previously solved the exercise, whether any problem slipped through or if all errors were found
7. Each one explains the solution they developed to their peer, showing the difficulties they had and how they solved them.

2. Study one or more anti-patterns, introduce to classmate and reinforce with exercise

Learners may study this antipattern to avoid it in the future with an exercise:

Note: It is important to do this with at least one peer.

1. Choose a topic already seen in class and select different parts of the topic for each learner to explain
2. Each one is to study the material, prepare a quick presentation, and search for examples to illustrate the explanation
3. Search for at least 1 exercise to be solved after your presentation
4. Choose whose turn it is to present
5. Start the presentation. The explanation should clarify everyone's difficulties. Showcase the possible errors (antipatterns) that may occur. In case some doubt remains, all may help search for answers if the presenter does not know enough.
6. Present the chosen exercise and ask colleagues to solve it
7. Check it together with bench test (table test) of the found solutions
8. Analyze what would happen if the antipattern existed in the code
9. Repeat steps 4 to 9 as many times as necessary for all to present their part

3. Introduce the error into a code and understand the consequences it generates

Learners may study this antipattern to avoid it in the future with an exercise:

Note: It is important to have a computer available to undertake the exercise.

1. Copy into the development environment some completed exercise from a previous class, a book, or the internet where the error (antipattern) may be inserted
2. execute the program and reason about what it does
3. insert the error (antipattern) in the code and try to execute it again
4. If there is a compilation error, note how the compiler present the error, so you can more easily understand what the compiler points to in cases of error
5. If the program executes, note how results are presented, trying to understand where the error is and how it behaves
6. Do this with multiple exercises, until you are certain that you understand the antipattern